

WOUNDS OF WISDOM
Intergenerational Transformation from Trauma to Resilience

UNIVERSITY OF BIRMINGHAM

Wounds of Wisdom *WoW*

JOURNEY OF INTER-GENERATIONAL TRANSFORMATION FROM TRAUMA TO RESILIENCE

The effects of trauma can be passed down through generations, but so can the resilience and healing.

The "Wounds of Wisdom (WoW) Journey of Inter-generational Transformation from Trauma to Resilience" is a groundbreaking initiative aimed at addressing the profound impact of trauma across generations and fostering resilience within affected communities. Research has consistently shown that trauma can have lasting effects not only on the individuals who directly experience it but also on their descendants. Studies, such as the groundbreaking work of Rachel Yehuda and others, have highlighted the transmission of trauma-related changes in DNA, which can influence the mental and physical health of future generations.

In Pakistan, as in many other parts of the world, families have experienced the devastating consequences of inter-generational trauma for decades. The trauma experienced by one generation can manifest as a legacy of pain, anxiety, and unresolved grief for their descendants. This cycle of suffering often impedes social progress, hinders community cohesion, and perpetuates a sense of helplessness among affected families.

The long-term impacts of inter-generational trauma on future generations in Pakistan are profound. Research has shown that children and grandchildren of individuals who have experienced trauma may be at an increased risk of mental health disorders, such as depression, anxiety, and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). Additionally, the cumulative stress of

living within trauma-affected families can affect physical health, leading to conditions like heart disease and autoimmune disorders. These ongoing effects not only burden the healthcare system but also hinder the country's socio-economic development. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that depression and anxiety disorders cost the global economy \$1 trillion per year in lost productivity.

"INTER-GENERATIONAL RESILIENCE: THE BUTTERFLY EFFECT"

Recognizing the urgency of addressing this issue, the "Wounds of Wisdom (WoW) Journey of Inter-generational Transformation from Trauma to Resilience" becomes particularly significant in Pakistan. By offering holistic support, including therapy, community engagement, and self-care programs.

The WOW Project employed the butterfly metaphor to illustrate the transformative journey of trauma to resilience.

Participants recognized the stages: acknowledging trauma (caterpillar), undergoing healing (chrysalis), and emerging stronger (butterfly). Through art and therapy, they embraced this metaphor, finding hope and strength in their own metamorphosis.

WoW provides a beacon of hope for individuals and families affected by intergenerational trauma. It seeks to break the cycle of suffering, empower families to confront their past, and promote resilience as a tool

Peer educators underwent comprehensive training on child and youth mental health, which equipped them to design and conduct mental health promotion workshops. Topics covered stigma, emotional literacy, trauma's impact, vulnerability, resilience, and selfcare. Concurrently, family consultation workshops were held, facilitating discussions among peer educators and intergenerational family advisers. These workshops explored the strengths and challenges of each generation within family units, using interactive and arts-based activities. A symbolic "tree and House" activity represented the generations, and participants also shared personal stories, deepening their understanding of familial dynamics and challenges.

for healing. This initiative's importance lies not only in alleviating the suffering of current generations but also in ensuring a brighter and more psychologically robust future for Pakistan, where families can thrive, and communities can flourish.

The research centered on two areas, Lyari and AB Cinia Lines Area in Karachi both facing unique challenges. Intergenerational family advisers, composed of young individuals, mothers, and grandmothers, were recruited from these communities. Grandmothers averaged between 55 and 70 years, mothers between 38 and 45 years, and young people between 14 and 18 years. Additionally, female peer educators, aged 18 to 24 and with diverse backgrounds, were selected from community volunteer network.

FIGURE 1:
Expressive Art Tree Drawing
Exploring Family's Intergenerational Strengths and Challenges

FIGURE 2:

Story of My Family Home- Expressive art intergenerational activity during family consultation workshop

- **Cultivate Community Networks:** Foster community support networks for all generations to connect and share experiences.
- **Cultural Inclusion Programs:** Tailor initiatives to the specific needs and preferences of the community.
- **Mental Health Accessibility:** Ensure accessible and culturally sensitive mental health services for children and youth.
- **Multi-Domain Collaboration:** Encourage collaboration among NGOs, government agencies, educational institutions, and healthcare providers.
- **Extended Impact Evaluation:** Establish a system for continuous monitoring and evaluation of mental health and well-being programs.

"TRANSFORMING PRACTICAL WISDOM FROM WOW - TIPS" TRAUMA:

- **Building Prevention Strategies:** Develop programs that focus on reducing the risk of trauma, such as conflict resolution workshops.
- **Introduce Trauma-Informed Education:** Include trauma-informed education in school curricula.
- **Teach Self-Care Practices:** Promote self-care practices like mindfulness, meditation, and exercise.
- **Encourage Resilience Building:** Implement programs to teach emotional strength and adaptability.
- **Plan Outdoor Activities:** Provide safe and welcoming outdoor spaces for outdoor events, especially for older generations.

These recommendations aim to create a resilient and emotionally healthy environment for future generations, breaking the cycle of intergenerational trauma and promoting overall well-being. In essence, the WOW-TIPS community awareness sessions were designed to empower individuals and families to break the cycle of intergenerational trauma, promote mental health and resilience, and create a supportive community environment where everyone, from grandmothers to youths, could thrive.

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ABOUT THE AUTHOR:

Sajida Hassan, a Ph.D. holder in Child Psychology from the University of Leicester, UK, is the Director and Founder of ICAN, an organization committed to enhancing the lives of children and adults through research-based training programs.

Her extensive international research collaborations with prestigious institutions like the University of Leicester, Wellcome Trust (UK),

Anna Freud Trust, and ESRC/NIHR in partnership with WACIT (UK) showcase her remarkable research skills. In recognition of her dedication, she received the 2023 Rights for Time Network Research Award from the University of Birmingham for her unique project on trauma to resilience transformation.

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